

Synthesis and spectral studies of transition metal complexes with 2,16-dimethyl-3,6,9,12,15,21-hexaaza-bicyclo[15.3.1]hencosa-1(21),2,15,17,19-pentaene

Sulekh Chandra*, Lokesh Kumar Gupta and Karuna Gupta

Department of Chemistry, Zakir Husain College (University of Delhi), J.L.N. Marg, New Delhi-110 002, India

E-mail : schandra_00@yahoo.com

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Complexes of transition metal ions with an azamacrocyclic ligand viz. 2,16-dimethyl-3,6,9,12,15,21-hexaaza-bicyclo[15.3.1]hencosa-1(21),2,15,17,19-pentaene (L^1) have been prepared. All the complexes were found to have the composition ML^1Cl_2 (where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II} or $M'L^1Cl_3$ (where $M' = Cr^{III}$ and Fe^{III}). Molar conductance measurements of Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes in DMSO correspond to 1 : 1 electrolytes, whereas ML^1Cl_3 and CuL^1Cl_2 are 1 : 2 electrolytes. Therefore complexes may be formulated as $[ML^1Cl]Cl$, $[M'L^1Cl]Cl_2$ and $[CuL^1]Cl_2$. All the complexes were characterized through elemental analyses, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility measurements, IR, electronic and EPR spectral studies.

In the past decades a great attention has devoted to the design and synthesis of Schiff bases with enhanced ability to selectively encapsulate given metal ions^{1,2}. In particular, macrocyclic and acyclic Schiff bases have successfully been proposed as excellent systems in the formation of mono-, homo- and hetero-polynuclear lanthanide complexes². Detailed investigations of their stereochemical, electronic, magnetic and catalytic properties have allowed the proposed of new, highly efficient molecular devices or probes for a number of specific applications³. Furthermore, they have been used as unconventional precursors in the formation of modified surfaces or otherwise not accessible mixed oxides⁴. Moreover, several studies have been addressed to the synthesis of suitable crown ethers or relative derivatives, containing cavities of different size and type and to their interaction with metal ions, with the specific aim of securing these metal ions into the coordination cavity and to study the transport phenomena across liquid membrane⁵.

In view of the above applications the syntheses and characterizations of transition metal complexes with such ligands are highly desirable. In this paper we report the syntheses and characterizations of transition metal complexes with 2,16-dimethyl-3,6,9,12,15,21-hexaazabicyclo[15.3.1]hencosa-1(21),2,15,17,19-pentaene (L^1).

Results and discussion

All the complexes found to have the composition ML^1Cl_2 (where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$) and $M'L^1Cl_3$ (where $M' = Cr^{III}$ and Fe^{III}). Molar conductance measurements of ML^1Cl_2 (where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}$ and Ni^{II}), in DMSO

correspond to 1 : 1 electrolytes whereas $M'L^1Cl_3$ and CuL^1Cl_2 are 1 : 2 electrolytes. Therefore complexes may be formulated as $[ML^1Cl]Cl$, $[M'L^1Cl]Cl_2$ and $[CuL^1]Cl_2$. The IR spectra of these complexes show a moderate intensity absorption in the range 1590–1650 cm^{-1} attributable to the imine ($\nu_{C=N}$)⁶ given in Table 2. The ligand behaves as pentadentate and coordinated to metal ion through five nitrogen (excluding pyridine nitrogen¹³) and the sixth position is occupied by the anion, except Cu^{II} complexes^{7,8} where all the macrocyclic donor sites of the ligand coordinated to the metal ion. Thus on the basis of IR spectral studies, it can be concluded that the metal has six coordinated geometry⁷.

Chromium(III) complex :

The magnetic moment value of the complex at RT is 3.74 B.M., close to the spin only value. The electronic spectrum shows bands at 11236 (ν_1), 18587 (ν_2) and 25000 cm^{-1} (ν_3) so the complex (MX_5Y type) may possess C_{4v} symmetry⁹. These bands can be assigned to the following transitions :

$${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g^a ({}^4T_{2g}) (\nu_1) = 10 Dq^{xy} - 35/4 Dt$$

$${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4B_{2g} ({}^4T_{2g}) (\nu_2) = 10 Dq^{xy}$$

$${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}^a ({}^4T_{1g}(F)) (\nu_3)$$

$$Dt = 2/7 (Dq^{xy} - Dq^z)$$

Various parameters were calculated and found to be $Dt = 733$, $Dq^{xy} = 2500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $Dq^z = 65.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The EPR spectrum of the complex recorded as polycrystalline sample at RT. The spectrum shows a single broad line with peak to peak separation of about 375 G. The g_{iso}

the C=S π bond was suggested as the decisive factor. The rate constants for the cycloadditions of *N*-methyl-*C*-phenylnitrone and *C,N*-diphenyl nitron to thione revealed little influence of solvent polarity. This militates against zwitterionic intermediates, but is in accordance with a concerted cycloaddition. There is qualitative evidence that, other double bonds involving elements of higher long periods are likewise superdipolarophiles and superdienophiles, respectively, in cycloaddition reactions. The steric effect would control the values of $\Delta H_{\text{cycloaddition}}$ and $\Delta S_{\text{cycloaddition}}$, but the former to a greater extent. The negative entropy term reveals the dominance of the loss of translational freedoms in making one molecule out of two⁷⁵. The inertness of thiobenzophenone toward nitrones appeared in new light, on estimating -5 kcal mol^{-1} for the conjugated energy of two phenyls with the C=S double bond, ultimately arrived at positive values for $\Delta G_{\text{cycloaddition}}$. With $\Delta S_{\text{cycloaddition}}$ kept constant, an increase of the dissociation enthalpy by -5 kcal mol^{-1} would result in a 4600 fold rise of $K_{\text{dissociation}}$ at -25°C .

The *ab initio* calculations on different levels were performed for cycloadditions of the parent nitron to thioformaldehyde and ethylene, respectively. An orientation complex (OC) was found for both cycloadditions. In the case of thioformaldehyde, the nature of the complex was of charge-transfer type as revealed by a perturbational analysis, whereas for ethylene as dipolarophile, the van der Waals character predominates. The transition structures for cycloaddition resembled closely the orientation complex with a shorter separation and a stronger distortion of the reactants. A negative energy of activation relative to the reactants, viz. $-2.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ (Becke 3LYP) and a small positive barrier ($+1.2 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) relative to the OC is calculated for thioformaldehyde as dipolarophile; the corresponding values for ethylene are $+13.7$ and $+15.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The perturbational analysis shows a strong HOMO_{nitron} – LUMO_{thioformaldehyde} interaction as the principal reason for the high thione reactivity⁷⁴.

C-Phenyl-*N*-(*p*-methylphenyl) nitron was found to be included in the β -cyclo-dextrin cavity in two different stoichiometries viz., 1G : 1H and 1G : 2H – the existence of which was proved by physical methods. The 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of the 1G : 2H complex with olefins in the solid state proceeds with accelerated rate and regioselection⁷⁸.

The first report of addition of a second nitron species onto the cycloadduct, derived from the same. This has been reported⁷⁹ after performing the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of 3,4-dehydromorpholine-4-oxide with the piperidides of

cinnamic acid and substituted cinnamic acids. The abnormal product formation possibly follows an iminium-oxonium mechanism.

This review outlines the recent developments in 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions of nitrones. An attempt has been made to be comprehensive rather than selective i.e. all journals rather than a selected few have been scanned. The emphasis has been on reactions and their explanation on mechanistic and theoretical grounds, rather than on applications. The latter could form the basis of a further review.

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plexes were recorded as powder samples at RT and LNT (for Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes) on an E-4 EPR spectrometer using DPPH as the g-marker.

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cycloadduct with moderate enantioselectivity⁶⁹. The reaction opens the possibility to construct versatile chiral intermediates for pyrrolizidine alkaloids.

The stereochemical outcome of the cycloaddition of formaldehyde *N*-benzyl nitrone with β - and γ -alkoxy α,β -unsaturated esters was investigated. These reactions were nicely rationalized on the basis of an interpretation of the "inside-alkoxy theory" emphasizing the electrostatic interactions in the reaction transition state. The force field approach, for evaluating the stereoselection was successfully extended to these reactions⁷⁰.

In order to develop a practical method for the construction of chiral molecules Inomata *et al.*⁷¹ have designed a novel chiral system possessing two metal centers utilizing tartaric acid esters. Based on this concept, asymmetric 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions of nitrones could be achieved by then, with a high level of stereocontrol.

Reactivity in 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions varies considerably from system to system and is best explained by the FMO model. According to this interpretation, 1,3-dipoles belong, depending on the number and nature of hetero atoms and on their substitution pattern, to one of three Sustmann categories. This classification determines whether a high reactivity is observed towards electron-deficient or electron-rich olefins, or to both of them. The more electron-deficient the dipolarophilic multiple bond, the faster electron-rich 1,3-dipoles undergo cycloadditions. Introduction of electron-attracting substituents into an ethylenic or acetylenic dipolarophile increases the rate constants by many power of 10. Both partial charges and rate constants appeared as consequences of the interaction energies of HOMO-LUMO pairs in an early transition state. The clarification of the "Schönberg reaction", e.g., the formation of the 1,3-dithiolane from diazomethane and two molecule of thiobenzophenone⁷², revealed an unusually high dipolarophilic activity of the C=S double bond⁷³. *N*-Methyl-*C*-phenyl nitrone and *N*-methyl-*C,C*-diphenylnitron are nucleophilic-electrophilic 1,3-dipoles which show a U-shaped reactivity profile but react preferentially with electron-acceptor substituted C=C bonds. Whereas many kinetic measurements have been performed for cycloadditions of substituted alkenes, comparable rate data on 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions to hetero double bonds, especially those involving elements of the second long period, are scarce⁷⁴.

1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions of *N*-methyl-*C,C*-diphenyl nitrone and *N*-methyl-*C*-phenylnitron with aliphatic thioketones are equilibrium reaction⁷⁴. The 1,4,2-oxathiazolidines were characterized and their dissociation

constants determined by ¹H NMR analysis and by visible spectrophotometry.

Rate constants for the cycloadditions of *N*-methyl-*C*-phenylnitron to thirty-six dipolarophiles in toluene at 85°C were measured by dilatometry; no compound with a C=S bond was included. A small selection reveals the acceleration by electron-withdrawing substituents ($10^5 k_2, M^{-1} s^{-1}$): 1-heptene, 0.33; methyl acrylate, 16; acrylonitrile, 31; fumaronitrile, 166; maleic anhydride, 1010; methyl propiolate, 200; DMAD, 5700. Thus, the reactivity of dimethyl acetylene dicarboxylate (DMAD) was at the top, 17000 times faster than 1-heptene. Other less active dipolarophiles required 120°C for convenient measurement. For reasons of comparison, the reactions of other dipolarophiles with this nitron were studied⁷⁵ in toluene.

Thiones are superdipolarophiles versus nitrones. The low activation energy must be the result of a diminished HOMO-LUMO gap. The high polarizability of the C=S bond, a rate-enhancing factor of the cycloadditions to thiones⁷⁶ may well be a consequence of a small HOMO-LUMO separation too. The C=S bond does not monopolize on low π (HOMO-LUMO) gap which should be widespread among π bonds in which elements of higher long period participate. For an unsubstituted double bond, the two FMO interactions, $HOMO_{nitron} - LUMO_{ethylene} = -12.5$ and $HOMO_{ethylene} - LUMO_{nitron} = -7.3 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, are not as different as in the case of a thioformaldehyde (-20.5 and $-3.3 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$). The high reactivity of thioformaldehyde derives thus from a dominant $HOMO_{nitron} - LUMO_{thioformaldehyde}$ interaction. The FMO energies for the two dipolarophiles as calculated by the PM3 method are: HOMO and LUMO of ethylene -10.64 and $+1.23 \text{ eV}$, HOMO and LUMO of thioformaldehyde -12.22 and -1.43 eV . The *RHF/6-31G** calculation provides the figures -10.19 and $+5.01 \text{ eV}$ for ethylene as well as -11.39 and $+1.54 \text{ eV}$ for thioformaldehyde. An additional non-negligible contribution to the reactivity of the C=S bond is derived from a difference in polar interactions between the C=C ($-1.9 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) and the C=S ($-6.4 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) systems. Houk *et al.*⁷⁷ calculated the $\pi-\pi^*$ energy difference of thioformaldehyde (*ab initio, split valence 3-21G*) to be 12.8 eV, i.e. 5.8 eV lower than that of formaldehyde.

Huisgen and Sustmann *et al.*⁷⁵ reported the superiority of thiones, even sterically hindered ones, versus *N*-methyl-*C*-phenylnitron, a nucleophilic-electrophilic 1,3-dipole. The equilibrium constants measured for 1,3-addition of nitrones to thiones apparently leave no doubt that the weakness of the C=S π bond was not responsible for the high reaction rates; a low HOMO-LUMO energy difference of

value is 2.077. The g value is calculated using expression $g = 2.0023(1 - 4\lambda/10Dq)$ where λ is the spin orbit coupling constant for the metal ion in the complex. Own¹⁰ noted that the reduction of spin-orbit coupling constant from the free ion value of 90 cm^{-1} for Cr^{III} can be employed as a measure of metal-ligand covalency. It is possible to define the covalency parameter analogous to nephelauxetic parameter which is the ratio of the spin-orbit coupling constant for the complex and free ion¹¹. $\lambda = 48.093$, $\lambda^* = \lambda/90 (\text{cm}^{-1}) = 0.534$.

Manganese(II) complex :

The magnetic moment value of the complex at RT is 5.96 B.M. corresponding to five unpaired electrons.

The electronic spectrum displays bands at $21276 (\nu_1)$, $24213 (\nu_2)$, $25641 (\nu_3)$ and $27027 \text{ cm}^{-1} (\nu_4)$. Single values of B and C have been obtained by the expressions

$${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g, {}^4A_{1g} ({}^4G) = 10B + 5C (\nu_2)$$

$${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g, ({}^4D) = 17B + 5C (\nu_4)$$

The energies of these transitions are independent of the crystal field splitting energy and depend¹² only on the parameters B and C . Dq could be evaluated with the help of energy level due¹³ to the transition ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4G)$. Slater Condon-shortly repulsion parameter F_2 and F_4 are related to the Racah parameter B and C as $B = F_2 - 5F_4$, $C = 35F_4$.

The electron-electron repulsion in the complexes is less than that in the free ion, resulting in an increased distance between electron and thus an effective increase in the size of the orbitals. On increasing delocalization the value of β decreases and is less than 1 in the complexes. The numerical value 786 cm^{-1} for the B of the free Mn^{II} ion has been used to calculate¹⁴ the value of β . The calculated value of β (0.92) and h_x indicate that the complex under study have appreciable covalent character. Value of other parameters are as $Dq = 974 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 886 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $C = 4038 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $F_2 = 978 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $F_4 = 115 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

EPR spectrum of the complex has been recorded as polycrystalline sample at RT. Polycrystalline sample give one broad isotropic signal centered at approximately the free electron g -value (2.01). In polycrystalline sample Mn^{II} complexes usually give broad signals attributed to forbidden transitions where ($M = \pm 1$) ($M =$ electron spin quantum number) and $\Delta m \neq 0$ (where $m =$ nuclear spin quantum number). Broadening due to immobilization of Mn^{II} ion in the ligand results because the rotational motion of Mn^{II} is highly restricted. Another origin of line broadening is spin relaxation, which is temperature dependent.

Iron(III) complex :

The magnetic moment of the complex is 5.89 B.M. cor-

responding to five unpaired electrons. The complex shows absorption bands at 23696 and 32573 cm^{-1} , but the assignment of bands is difficult. It is very unlikely that the spectra of iron(III) derivatives, which are more covalent than those of manganese(II), can be described in terms of single values of B and C . This is because of the oxidizing nature of the iron(III) species, charge transfer from ligand to metal are quite common.

Cobalt(II) complex :

This complex shows magnetic moment 4.98 B.M. at RT indicating spin quartet coordinate square pyramidal or trigonal bipyramidal and six coordinate octahedral cobalt complex.

Electronic spectrum of the complex under study displays a band at $9344 \text{ cm}^{-1} \nu_1$ and other band in the charge transfer region. So, transition might have mixed with charge transfer band or not resolved due to intense charge transfer band. Very weak band at 18518 cm^{-1} is assigned as ν_2 transition. The spectrum is characteristic of an octahedral geometry of cobalt complexes. Various ligand field parameters Dq , β and B were calculated using Orgel energy level diagram¹⁵. $Dq = 1032 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 333 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.30$.

EPR spectra were recorded at LNT because of spin-lattice relaxation and the two g values were found i.e. $g_{\parallel} = 3.55$, $g_{\perp} = 2.866$.

Copper complex :

The magnetic moment of the complex at RT is 1.92 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired electron (Table 1).

The electronic spectrum of copper(II) complex in DMSO

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of the metal complexes* with L¹

Complex and Molecular formula	Colour	MW	Molar	Yield %	μ_{eff} B.M.
		Calcd.	conductance		
		(Found)	$\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$		
$[\text{Cr}(\text{L}^1)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$	Black	474.5	100	75	3.74
$\text{CrC}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{H}_{28}\text{Cl}_3$		(474)			
$[\text{Mn}(\text{L}^1)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$	Dark	441.9	98	85	5.96
$\text{MnC}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{H}_{28}\text{Cl}_2$	brown	(442.5)			
$[\text{Fe}(\text{L}^1)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$	Grey	478.3	112	68	5.89
$\text{FeC}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{H}_{28}\text{Cl}_3$		(477.8)			
$[\text{Co}(\text{L}^1)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$	Black	445.9	115	45	4.98
$\text{CoC}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{H}_{28}\text{Cl}_2$		(444.8)			
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)]\text{Cl}_2$	Dark	450.5	216	78	1.92
$\text{CuC}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{H}_{28}\text{Cl}_2$	brown	(450)			

L¹ = 2,16-Dimethyl-3,6,9,12,15,21-hexaaza-bicyclo[15.3.1]henicosal(21),2,15,17,19-pentaene.

*All the compounds gave satisfactory metal and elemental analysis.

solution exhibits a single broad band at 15083 cm^{-1} (Table 2) due to *d-d* transition. The other band at 34602 cm^{-1} is charge transfer band.

Complexes	$\nu(>\text{C}=\text{N})\text{ cm}^{-1}$	Spectral bands ^a $\lambda_{\text{max}}(\text{cm}^{-1})$
[Cr(L ¹)Cl]Cl ₂	1599	11236, 18587, 25000
[Mn(L ¹)Cl]Cl	1605	21276, 24213, 25641, 27027
[Fe(L ¹)Cl]Cl ₂	1650	23696, 32573
[Co(L ¹)Cl]Cl	1645	9344, 18518
[Cu(L ¹)Cl ₂]	1649	15083

^aElectronic spectra are recorded in DMSO solution.

An EPR spectrum of complex at RT shows a broad peak with peak to peak separation of 300 G. The g_{iso} value is 2.098, while EPR spectrum of the complex at LNT shows four line spectrum. This may be due to the copper coupling and no hyperfine coupling due to the coupling with nitrogen atoms is observed. Thus simulation of EPR spectra of the complex leads three different principal values of g . This fact indicates that the copper(II) ion of complex is present in rhombically distorted ligand fields¹⁶. Copper(II) complex $g_3 > g_2$ (or g_1), typical of tetragonal copper(II) where the tetragonal distortion takes the form of elongation of the axial bonds. Using the approximated equation¹⁷ taken from ligand field theory for the g value $g_{\parallel} = 2.0023(1 - 4\alpha_{\parallel}^2\lambda/E(d_{x^2-y^2} - d_{xy}))$ where λ is the spin orbit coupling constant (-828 cm^{-1}) of the copper(II) ion. α_{\parallel}^2 is the orbital reduction factor, cause by the spreading of the unpaired electron out of the ligand, and E is the energy corresponding to the split between the two sets of molecular orbitals, taken from the electronic spectrum, it is possible to determine approximate values for α_{\parallel}^2 about 0.79 for the complex. The magnitude of this value suggests considerable covalent character for the bonding to copper. From EPR at LNT three g values are calculated and their corresponding A values. The values are as follows :

$$g_1 = 2.033 (A_1 = 60 \times 10^4\text{ cm}^{-1}), g_2 = 2.133 (A_2 = 50 \times 10^4\text{ cm}^{-1}) \text{ and } g_3 = 2.4 (A_3 = 190 \times 10^4\text{ cm}^{-1}).$$

Thus on the basis of magnetic susceptibility and molar conductance measurements, IR, electronic and EPR spectral studies and the subsequent discussion for the complexes given above, the following structure may be proposed for these complexes (Fig. 1).

Experimental

The ligand prepared, due to poor yield can't be used for

Fig. 1. Suggested structure of complexes with L¹.

complexation. So template method is used for the preparation of complexes. Otherwise also template method is advantageous because by employing a metal ion with certain steric requirements or preferences, a reaction may be controlled and thereby a particular macrocyclic product may be obtained at the expense of an undesired macrocyclic product.

Preparation of complexes :

To an ethanolic solution of 2,6-diacetylpyridine (1.5 mmol, 0.244 g), ethanolic solution of metal salt (1.5 mmol) was added. After few minutes of heating ethanolic solution of tetraethylenepentamine (1.5 mmol, 0.283 g) was added slowly. Stirring and heating was maintained during the addition and the solution was then refluxed. Duration of refluxing varies for different metal ions. On cooling a colored precipitate formed, was filtered and washed with cold ethanol and dried under vacuum.

Microanalyses (C, H and N) of these complexes were carried out on a Carlo-Erba-1106 elemental analyzer. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 instrument as nujol mulls/KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO solution on a Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. Molar conductance is measured on an Elico conductivity bridge (type C M 82 T). Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on Gouy Balance at RT by using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as calibrant. EPR spectra of the com-

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